

FULLY PRINTED PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELLS AND MODULES

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ABSTRACT: In few years, the perovskite (PVSK) solar technology reached high efficiency on lab scale cells. The upscaling of PVSK photovoltaic (PV) technology from small area cells (PSCs) to modules, and the related industrial and economical transition, is achievable by scalable and low-cost manufacturing processes/materials and module design/interconnection patterning. Carbon-based PSCs are attracting attention because of low-cost, durability and printability (high throughput), but few works are present about modules. On the other hand, the most efficient and stable FAPI PVSK is mainly deposited by different techniques with a gold counter-electrode. Here, we changed the paradigm by optimizing the materials composition, by blade coating the full stack out of glove-box. The laser ablation strategy in combination with printing techniques were adopted to fabricate a fully printed module (preliminary prototype). We got 20.8%, 15% and 13.2% efficiency on gold- and carbon-based cells (0.5 cm²), and carbon-based module, respectively.

Keywords: photovoltaic, perovskite, module manufacturing, scaling-up, carbon, printing

1 INTRODUCTION

Owing to their unique physical-chemical properties, [1], [2] organometal halide perovskites permitted to develop a solution process photovoltaic (PV) technology able to deliver power conversion efficiencies higher than any thin film PV and closely resembling the one of silicon. [3] Thanks to a fine tuning of material compositions, device architectures and fabrication processes the efficiency of perovskite (PVSK) solar cells (PSCs) reached 26.1% for the single junction and 33.9% when used in tandem with silicon. [3], [4] The efficiency transfer from laboratory cells to module devices is of paramount importance to exploit at market level the PVSK PV technology. The uniformity of the deposition and the losses induced by front contact and cell interconnections are the main obstacles for scaling-up the cell to a module level. [5] The module design and the interconnection patterning can face and limit these issues. The losses due to the layers' inhomogeneity are related to the difficulties in transferring to module devices deposition processes and material compositions optimized for the small area cells. [6] In this context, the polycrystalline nature of solution-processed PVSK layers induces defects, such as at grain boundaries and vacancies during the fabrication process. [7] A scalable, repeatable and optimized process is the baseline to obtain high efficiency devices and to upscale the photovoltaic technology. [8]–[11] Recently, FAPbI₃ has been developed as an effective absorber, with a narrower band gap of 1.47 eV compared to MAPbI₃. Therefore, FA is used to replace MA to reduce the bandgap toward a more ideal range. In literature, researchers scaled up to module the FAPbI₃ formulation by air-assisted bar-coating, [12] spin-coating, [13] or blade coating techniques, [14] but still adopting unstable HTM (Hole Transporting Materials) and gold counter-electrode. Organic HTMs are considered the ideal p-type semiconductor materials because of the tunable energy level, the good hole mobility and the solution preparation. [15], [16] The drawbacks of some of these HTMs for the commercial applications are

the high-synthetic and doping cost, and the thermal instability. [17] The widely used gold cathode materials for high efficiency cells and large area modules [18]–[20] are corroded by halogen ions, need high energy process during the device fabrication and are not cheap [21], [22]. Carbon-based perovskite solar cell technology can face these issues by replacing the gold counter electrode with the cheap and stable carbon black/graphite layer. [23]–[25]. In the low-temperature architecture, the carbon layer is deposited directly on top of the adsorber layer and the PVSK can have large crystals because it is not constricted in the pore size of the carbon layer. Moreover, the hole transporting material can be easily inserted to improve the hole-extraction and reduce the non-radiative recombination at the perovskite/carbon interface.

In this work, we stabilized the α -FAPbI₃ phase by doping with methylammonium chloride (MACl) and achieved a short-circuit current density above 24 mA/cm² and efficiency approaching 21%. We performed module designing and related interconnections optimization, exploited interfacial defects passivation to suppress nonradiative recombination losses, to improve charge carrier extraction and photovoltage on module device, and optimized the deposition process to have a homogeneous large area coating. Finally, we report fully low-temperature and fully printed carbon-based FAPI PVSK cells (0.5 cm²) and modules able to achieve a champion efficiency more than 15%.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We adopted the c-TiO₂/SnO₂ (tin oxide) as ETL, a formamidinium-based lead triiodide (FAPbI₃) as PVSK, phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) as passivation material, Spiro-OMeTAD as HTL (Hole Transporting Layers) and gold as counter-electrode. The full stack, except for the gold, was deposited by the blade-coating technique at low-temperature and out of the glove-box.. We optimized the ETL and the PVSK layer. Although SnO₂ ETL fabricated by different methods (spin-coating,

chemical bath deposition, atomic layer deposition) could benefit the elimination of the hysteresis, the reason why the results are not reproducible is still unclear. [26] Here, we investigated the SnO₂ colloid precursor from Alfa Aesar by adding NaOH to stabilize the PH value and reduce the hysteresis. Therefore, the material has a wider process window if used out of glove-box by blade-coating technique. Moreover, we worked on the composition to improve the Voc. About the PVSK, we introduced into FAPbI₃ formulation CsI and MACl to shrink the lattice and stabilize the PVSK phase. The MACl will be eliminated during the annealing process at 160 °C. The FAPbI₃ PVSK deposition process was based on a double step procedure out of glove-box. After the meniscus formation in the first step, the blade-coating machine (Charon, Cicci Research) deposits the PVSK precursor assisted by a heated dry air flow to reach the supersaturated state of PVSK film. A subsequent 2-propanol (IPA-Isopropyl Alcohol) anti-solvent quenching step is performed by the same deposition method to remove the DMSO excess and force crystallization of PVSK. [27] Then the substrate is annealed at 160 °C for 10 min to nullify the yellow phase and to clearly see the PbI₂ phase (**Figure 1**). XRD shows α phase (101), (012), (021), (202), and (211) crystal planes of the cubic PVSK phase (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: XRD patterns of the PVSK films before and after PEAI deposition.

The synergic effect of the antisolvent and gas quenching causes instant supersaturation of precursor solution and grants fast nucleation and rapid removal of solvents, promoting the homogeneity of PVSK film in the whole substrate. The polycrystalline nature of solution-processed PVSK layers induces defects and trap states, such as at grain boundaries and vacancies during the fabrication process. [7] The PVSK surface passivation by phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) is one of the most efficient methods to suppress nonradiative recombination losses and to improve charge carrier extraction and photovoltage. The XRD pattern (**Figure 1**) shows a peak at 12.7° (reduced because of the PEAI) related to the PbI₂ excess in the crystalline 3D PVSK film. [28]

The adopted optimization results in an efficiency of 20.8% (Hysteresis Index HI=1.03) on 0.5 cm² active area (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: JV curves of the best fabricated 0.5 cm² cells.

Then, we substituted PEAI, Spiro-OMeTAD and the gold counter-electrode with HTAB (hexyl trimethylammonium bromide), P3HT and a low-temperature carbon (Dyename) layer, respectively, deposited by blade-coating technique in ambient air to achieve a fully printed perovskite device (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: The full stack printed in ambient air.

The efficiency was 15% and the main affected parameters were FF and Voc because of the unoptimized interface between PVSK and carbon (work in progress). The P1 (FTO scribing)-P2 ablation steps by a laser source (here ps-UV laser) are crucial to obtain the module device. The P2 removes the full stack (ETL/PVSK/Passiv./HTL) deposited on FTO from the vertical connection areas to series connect two adjacent cells with the subsequent electrode deposition. The realization of several laser areas with different fluences and number of pulses is useful to evaluate the laser ablation threshold of a material that is a heterogeneous stack. The main constrain is to avoid the TCO damaging to limit the contact resistance between the carbon counter electrode and the TCO. We analyzed the FTO sheet resistance (7 ohm/sq.), the stack thickness (900 nm) and the transfer length measurement (TLM) to minimize possible losses due to the laser process. Then, we deposited by a semi-automatic screen-printing technique the carbon counter-electrode by using an appropriate screen mesh to obtain the electrical insulation between the counter electrodes of adjacent cells. The improved deposition strategy and cells interconnection resulted in a max module efficiency of 13.2% (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: IV curve of the full printed module.

3 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we presented the preliminary efforts to fabricate low-temperature fully printed FAPI-PVSK cells and modules out of glove-box based on carbon counter-electrode by improving structural design, material chemistry, and fabrication process (coating and laser ablation). The reported simple and reproducible method represent an outstanding baseline to be transferred to a scalable fabrication procedure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, through a FET Proactive research and innovation action under grant agreement No. 101084124 (DIAMOND).

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